

The Effect of Post Cure Time and Temperature on the Mechanical Properties of Pultruded S2-Glass/Epoxy Rods

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ABSTRACT

This paper describes the results of experiments designed to determine the effect of post cure conditions on the mechanical properties of 0.375 inch diameter pultruded S2-Glass and EPON 9310 epoxy rods. The studies were conducted to determine the processing conditions that would result in the highest possible measurements for short beam shear and tensile strength in the pultruded material. Tests of compressive and flexural strength were also conducted.

Samples were made by first producing approximately 300 feet of rod using processing conditions previously determined to result in good mechanical properties. The pultruded rods were cut into 12 inch lengths and subjected to various post cures. Each set of 20 rods was processed at one of the nine possible combinations of three different times (5, 10 or 60 minutes) and three different temperatures (135°C, 160°C and 200°C). The test matrix therefore contained nine different time/temperature pairs, plus the non-post cured parts, with six samples for each of the 4 mechanical property tests. A total of 240 tests were performed.

Resulting test data showed that the range of post cure times and temperatures selected for study had no significant effect on any of the mechanical properties measured. As a result of this study, the post cure stage was eliminated from a production process designed to automate the manufacture of a cable for towing underwater electronics systems. Elimination of the need for a post cure resulted in a major cost savings to the program.

Keywords: Pultrusion, S-Glass, Epoxy, Post Cure, Extrusion, Tow Cables

1. Introduction

American Composite Technology specializes in the the development of automated manufacturing methods for high performance advanced composite material products. One of the company's recently completed R&D efforts involved the development of a method for producing continuous 1,000 foot lengths of hydrodynamically contoured cable. The cable is designed to be used as the link between helicopter or surface ship-borne mine or submarine detection systems and their towed underwater electronics. Because the towed systems move rapidly through the water, fluid dynamic drag minimization is important. A high tensile strength structural member is required to minimize the drag-producing frontal area of the cable. A tough but flexible fairing is needed for streamlining. A schematic of the cross section of the cable design that meets these as well as other operational requirements is illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Cross Section of Cable for Underwater Towed Electronics Systems

The cable is fabricated from three major components using a hybrid pultrusion/co-extrusion process. The pultruded S-2 Glass/epoxy strength member is designed to carry axial tensile loads in excess of 10,000 pounds. The strength member is produced in lengths as great as 1,500 feet and stored on a large diameter spool prior to final assembly of the components into an integrated cable. A circular thermoplastic extrusion is fabricated in a separate operation. This cable contains four fiber optic conductors for transmission of data to and from a surface vehicle to the towed body. Six copper conductors are also included in the cable assembly for power transmission. These two pre-manufactured parts are then brought together in a co-extrusion process to produce the completed cable by applying an airfoil-shaped hydrodynamic fairing

made from a thermoplastic elastomer material. The cord of the finished assembly is approximately 2.5 inches. The 1,000 foot long finished product is designed to store leading edge down on a five foot diameter spool. This design has a number of advantages over previous cables, including lighter weight from the use of plastics and composites, lower cost from the use of automated manufacturing methods, higher data rates from the inclusion of the fiber optic cables, and lower drag and acoustic noise due to the clean hydrodynamic shape.

To be commercially viable, composite material structures require processing technologies capable of repeatedly producing high quality parts that can be assembled into systems which are less costly than competing products. American Composite Technology has worked toward the development of automated production methods required to allow composite structures to reach this goal. The combination of advanced production methods and design concepts that treat the structure as a system rather than a collection of individual parts makes it possible to cost-effectively exploit the tremendous performance advantages of fiber reinforced composites.

Pultrusion is the production process which offers the greatest potential for simultaneously meeting low cost and high quality goals. Figures 2 and 3 illustrate the motivation behind the adaptation of the pultrusion process to the production of large composite structures. The two figures show the estimated cost and cycle time for a graphite/epoxy stiffened panel made at an annual production rate of 2000 units. The analysis shows that pultruding the baseline part would be at least 2.5 times less costly than filament winding, the next most efficient of the alternate methods. Parts made with prepreg materials using a variety of hand and automated layup methods were predicted to be up to 5.5 times more costly than the pultruded part.

Figure 2: Composite Production Technology Cost Comparison¹

¹ Krolewski, S., and Gutowski, T., 1986, "Effect of the Advanced Composite Fabrication Process on Part Cost," *18th International SAMPE Technical Conference*, Oct 7-9, pp 83-97.

The low cost of pultruded composite hardware can be attributed to a variety of factors. Because the process requires little operator input other than to maintain the material supply, labor costs are very low compared to other alternatives for moderate production runs. Pultrusion machinery is relatively inexpensive when compared to other automated composite production hardware, and tooling costs are also low. Pultrusion generally employs the least costly forms of the constituent matrix and reinforcing materials, and very little of the material is wasted.

Figure 3: Composite Production Technology Cycle Time Comparison¹

Figure 3 compares the cycle times for the various processes. Except for pultrusion, all the production techniques in the study are based on the construction of discrete components. With all other production techniques, some or all of the production process steps must be individually repeated for each item that is manufactured. Cost of repetitive operations can greatly increase the price of the finished component. Only pultrusion produces completely cured composite parts on a continuous basis, and is therefore able to fabricate cured structures of any length at rates 15 to 40 times faster than alternative methods. It can be reasonably assumed that the comparisons in Figures 2 and 3 would be even more favorable to pultrusion if larger components and products requiring longer production runs were compared.

The purpose of the work described in this paper was the identification of the processing conditions that would produce the best combination of mechanical properties in the pultruded strength member. In particular, a test program was devised to determine if the use of a post cure cycle would result in a significant improvement in tensile and short beam shear properties. The post cure would be implemented by moving the glass/epoxy strength member through a length of in-line oven to maintain the product at an elevated temperature after the

component had exited the pultrusion die, where its primary cure cycle is completed.

2. Experimental

The test program was conducted using approximately 300 feet of pultruded 0.375 inch diameter S2-Glass/epoxy solid rod using a set of processing parameters previously found to result in high quality parts. Fiber volume of the unidirectionally reinforced rod was approximately 63%. 55 tows of 12K Owens Corning S2-Glass fiber with epoxy sizing was used. The epoxy used was Shell EPON 9310. The pultruded rod stock was subjected to a variety of different post-processing times and temperature combinations prior to mechanical testing. In particular, 20 samples each were subjected to 5, 10 or 60 minutes at temperatures of 135°C, 165°C or 200°C. A control group of samples not subjected to a post cure was included in the test matrix.

Post cure was accomplished by preheating an oven to the desired post cure temperature, then placing rod materials into the oven for the desired lengths of time. The rods were initially at room temperature prior to loading into the oven.

Five to seven samples from each pair of post cure time and temperature were subjected to tests for tensile strength, compressive strength, short beam shear strength and flexural strength. Tests were conducted using an Instron Model 4507 universal tester with a 44,960 pound load cell accurate to $\pm 1\%$ of the indicated load. A cross head speed of 0.050 inches per minute was used for all tests. The results of these tests are described in the following sections.

3. Tensile Strength Tests

Tensile tests were conducted using ASTM 3916, Standard Test for Tensile Properties of Pultruded Glass Fiber Reinforced Plastic Rod. Test specimens had a 4.75 inch gage length, and were held using mechanical wedge grips. The specimen was modified from that specified by the ASTM test by machining a small circumferential groove around the center of the test specimen. This groove forced the failure to occur in the gage length. Without the groove, the failures tended to occur within the mechanical grips due to the stress concentration introduced by the clamping action.

Results of the mechanical tests are shown in Figure 4. Each point in this and the following plots of test results represents the numerical average of between five and seven individual tests of specimens subjected to identical post cure time and

temperatures. Failure stresses reported in this figure were calculated by dividing the measured failure load by the reduced section area of the minimum groove diameter.

Figure 4: Tensile Strength of Post Cured S2-Glass/Epoxy Rod

Figure 4 shows that tensile strength is generally unaffected by post cure. Average strengths for each time and temperature post cure combination scatters around the 244,000 psi tensile strength of the non-post cured control specimens. This result is not unexpected, since post cure would influence the matrix dominated properties to a greater extent than the fiber-dominated tensile strength.

4. Flexural Strength Tests

Flexural strength tests were conducted using ASTM D4476, Flexural Properties of Fiber Reinforced Plastic Rods. Test specimens were 6.0 inches long, and were subjected to a ramping 3 point bending load until failure occurred. Failure was generally on the compressive side of the test specimen. Results of the flexure tests are shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Flexure Strength of Post Cured S2-Glass/Epoxy Rod

The flexural strength of the pultruded rods was found to be relatively unaffected by the post cure conditions of this study. Test data scatters around the 145,000 psi flexural strength of the non-post cured baseline test samples.

5. Short Beam Shear Strength Tests

Short beam shear strength tests were conducted using ASTM D4475, Apparent Horizontal Shear Strength of Pultruded Reinforced Plastic Rods by the Short Beam Method. Test specimens were 2.25 inches long, and were subjected to increasing levels of 3 point bending load until shear failure occurred. Results of the shear strength tests are shown in Figure 6.

The quantitative values obtained from both the flexural and short beam shear tests are known not to represent any single material property of the test specimens. Failures that occur when these two test methods are employed are a result of a complex stress state induced by the mechanics of the testing technique. The test values do serve a useful function, however, even if the qualitative values are difficult to interpret. The test results do tend to rise and fall in relation to positive and negative changes to processing techniques. Because the matrix properties are most influenced by processing conditions, the short beam shear and flexural strength values are most sensitive to the processing changes.

Figure 6: Flexure Strength of Post Cured S2-Glass/Epoxy Rod

The short beam shear strength results show that this property is also relatively insensitive to the post cure times and temperatures used in this study. Test data scatters around the 6,750 psi short beam shear strength of the non-post cured baseline data. Since the short beam shear strength is a matrix dominated material property, it was expected that this test would be most indicative of the potential benefits of a post cure step in the manufacturing process.

6. Compressive Strength Tests

Compressive strength tests were conducted using ASTM D695-85, Standard Test Method for Compressive Properties of Rigid Plastics. Test specimens were approximately 1 inch long, and were subjected to increasing levels of compressive load until failure occurred. Failure was generally some combination of end brooming, longitudinal splitting, crushing and buckling. Results of the compressive tests are shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Compressive Strength of Post Cured S2-Glass/Epoxy Rod

The compressive test data indicated more scatter than the other three tests. This is not surprising given the inherent difficulty in performing compressive tests. It is widely recognized that compressive test results are highly sensitive to small variations in specimen preparation and test set up. This sensitivity is manifested in the variety of failure modes that can occur in a compressive test specimen. Most specimens in this study exhibited a combination of two or more failure modes. From the present data set, there did appear to be a trend toward increasing compressive strength with increasing post cure time in the samples held at 165°C. It is unclear whether this finding actually demonstrates an improvement of compressive strength, or is simply scatter in the data. In any event, all test specimens produced strengths within approximately 10,000 psi of the 92,000 psi compressive strength of the non-post cured specimens.

7. Conclusions

An extensive mechanical testing program showed no significant improvement in tensile, shear, flexural and compressive strength after subjecting 0.375 inch diameter pultruded S-Glass/epoxy rods to three different elevated temperatures for three different lengths of time. Based on the results of these tests, the strength member for the cable was produced without subjecting the part to a post cure of any kind. The ability to eliminate the post cure step without degrading

mechanical properties of the strength member greatly simplified the manufacturing process, and led to greatly increased manufacturing speed and reduced processing costs.